

Navigating TechCentral's Architecture and Design Ecosystem

Report by coursework students of UTS 94663
Navigating Entrepreneurial Ecosystems and
Initiating Change, 2021 cohort

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Foreword

This report is part of a series of student generated series about entrepreneurial ecosystems. Each report is a derivative of their coursework, conducted in collaboration with multiple industry partners and interviews with stakeholders in the ecosystem. The subject, 94663 Navigating Entrepreneurial Ecosystems and Initiating Change, is a core subject in the Diploma in Innovation at TD School and a popular elective across other UTS degree programs. The subject was piloted as part of the launch for the Sydney School of Entrepreneurship in 2017¹ and draws directly on Martin's prior experience in visualising entrepreneurial ecosystems.²

The subject runs for three weeks in July, during which students are tasked with defining and exploring an entrepreneurial ecosystem, understanding its history and visualising its current state. Based on that knowledge, they then develop proposals that will bring the ecosystem forward.

The reports reflect the work that was presented publicly to invited guests and stakeholders in the subject, as well as members of the public who joined the presentations via the publicly available event page.

Methodology

The cohort of 50+ students was divided into random teams, each of which could choose their own ecosystem to focus on, with the only caveat being that it relates to TechCentral. Generally, the ecosystems were geographically in the immediate vicinity of TechCentral³, but varied significantly in terms of their sectoral focus.

Each team was instructed to consider the types of stakeholder based on Stam's seminal (2015) review of ecosystem factors. The general method of this study follows our own method of evaluating ecosystems that has evolved over years of experience, in consultation with an Australian wide network of ecosystem researchers. While our process is not yet well documented, it is entirely consistent with the 2018 guide produced by the German Society for International Collaboration,⁴ promoted by the Aspen Network of Development Entrepreneurs (ANDE). Teams adopt a qualitative approach, involving interviewing a broad range of participants to extract insights on their interpersonal connections and interrelations between factors and to identify specific opportunities for change. Each participant is believed to have a clear view of their immediate ecosystem, from which teams stitch together the more holistic view of how the ecosystem works.

The method can be tailored to specific ecosystems, ranging from rural communities through to internationally acclaimed innovation precincts. The breadth of Stam's framework and this method enables pushing back against the myth that innovation and entrepreneurship is primarily the domain of high-tech startups and VCs. While they do play a very important role, they are not the only organisations that matter to create economic growth (Brown & Mason, 2017; Spigel et al., 2020).

Field research for coursework follows the same principles as field research for academic purposes. As a result, the students' work mirrored the process of ecosystem research conducted by Martin Bliemel, for which he has ethics approval (HREC# ETH18-3020).

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¹ Bliemel, M., Schweitzer, J., Roy, G., Keitel, A., Nicolas, L., Miles, M., ... & Griffith, S. (2019, November). Herding cats to co-create cross-university courses in record time. *UIIN University-Industry Interaction Conference 2019*. University Industry Innovation Network.

² Bliemel, M. (2019). University-based entrepreneurial ecosystems and their visualisations. *University-Industry Innovation Magazine*.

³ <https://www.uts.edu.au/news/innovation/welcome-neighbourhood-tech-central>

⁴ <https://www.goethe.de/resources/files/pdf197/5.-guide-for-mapping-the-entrepreneurial-ecosystem.pdf>

Contents

Foreword	3
Methodology	3
Acknowledgements	3
Abstract	5
1 Evolution of the Entrepreneurial Ecosystem	5
1.1 History & Evolution	5
1.2 EE Map Breakdown	6
1.2.1 Defining the Ecosystem	6
1.2.2 Entrepreneurial Ecosystem Map	6
2 Leverage Proposal	8
2.1 Ecosystem Future	8
2.2 Analysis of opportunities and fragmentation in the current ecosystem	9
2.3 The Levers in The Ecosystem	9
2.3.1 Lever 1: Integrating the entrepreneurial ecosystem through education and government Support with one central platform.	9
2.3.2 Lever 2: Growth of Green Startups	11
3 Expected Value of Proposals	13
References	14

Abstract

This report aims to reflect and present the Architecture and Design industry within the City of Sydney's entrepreneurial ecosystem (hereafter, EE). Findings in this report will provide an in-depth look at the history of the industry and key stakeholders in an attempt to propose an envisioned development plan which highlights opportunities for the ecosystem to evolve.

Through analysing, researching and interviewing key stakeholders within the ecosystem, this report paper will aim to recognise and explore the history and its current state, to facilitate the future development of the space

1 Evolution of the Entrepreneurial Ecosystem

1.1 History & Evolution

The architecture of Sydney, Australia's oldest city, is characterised by a vast juxtaposition of old and modern buildings during the city's 200-year history, rather than by a single architectural style. The Rocks tour begins around 1780 with Captain James Cook's visit and includes structures constructed until 1950. It also points out that without the green banning movement of the 1970s, The Rocks would not be as rich in architectural heritage as it is today (Sheard, 2017). Furthermore, the Green ban movement is the act of construction labourers who built office-block towers, shopping centres, and luxury apartments that were increasingly encroaching on natural spaces or replacing older-style business and residential buildings in Sydney started an unusual kind of environmental activism. The construction workers refused to work on projects that were harmful to the environment or to society. This green ban movement, as it became known, was the first of its type in the world. (Burgmann, 2011).

While under Governor Macquarie's patronage and protection, Francis Greenway (1777-1837) created some of Australia's greatest colonial structures. St. James Church and the Supreme Court in Sydney City, as well as St Matthew's Church in Windsor, are examples of existing structures (State Library NSW, n.d). Below is the Australian architectural style by order ;

The colony was so low in proper skills and tools for the first two decades of its existence that most buildings produced were of poor quality and in continual need of maintenance (Sheard, 2017). According to Sheard, 2017, this began to alter in 1810, when Major-General Lachlan Macquarie was appointed Governor of New South Wales. Macquarie instituted a set of building rules and partnered with Francis Greenway, a convicted forger and architect who went on to become Australia's first government architect and supervised the construction of high-quality structures such as the Hyde Park Barracks and the Cadman Cottage, Sydney's oldest residential structure still standing.

Increased prosperity and an economic upturn in the immediate years following World War I led to a construction boom, as well as the introduction of several Art Deco and early modernist buildings and new building technology from the United States, according to Sydney Inter-War (Sheard, 2017).

Nowadays, the institution that has responsibility for the architecture segment is the Government Architect New South Wales (GANSW). GANSW was established in the 1990s, when the Government Architect has reported separately in a second position, as an advisor to the government, and serves on different committees and boards in relation to heritage protection, architecture, and design since the consultant service began working on commercial principles. GANSW provides architectural, urban design, and landscape architecture strategic design leadership and collaborates across government, the commercial sector, and the community to improve social, environmental, and economic outcomes for NSW and all of our communities by integrating design knowledge (GANSW, n.d).

1.2 EE Map Breakdown

1.2.1 Defining the Ecosystem

An entrepreneurial ecosystem (EE) can be defined as a conceptual framework that encompasses a variety of different perspectives within a geographical region of entrepreneurship and operates through direct and indirect interactions (Fredin & Lidén, 2020). Our geographical boundaries include Sydney CBD

1.2.2 Entrepreneurial Ecosystem Map

The following map is a visual representation of the Architectural industry and aims to represent the most relevant stakeholders including, major organisations, educational institutions, governmental and regulatory agencies. Further, the ecosystems recognise their interconnected nature based on research findings and depicted by the pointed arrows.

Our map is both inclusive and accurate in the connections that are made between stakeholder groups and categories. Our map has been designed to resemble the complex relations between organisations and institutions in reference to each other and the wider ecosystem.

Our ecosystem has been colour coded to resemble each systemic and framework condition with any given ecosystem. By colour coding the different conditions, the complexity of the ecosystem can be easier understood at a glance whilst also being able to clearly follow the connections.

2 Leverage Proposal

2.1 Ecosystem Future

With emerging trends constantly appearing in contemporary society, the architectural industry's ecosystem evolves to adapt to modern stakeholders. It is said that in 2026, Sydney will dynamically grow in the professional services industries, meaning that architects will be more valued and jobs will be produced for this service (Matt Wade, 2016). TMD Studio (2017) displays what areas of the specific ecosystem would potentially include over 10 years such as including; collaboration with specialists, involvement with digital enterprises and also entities to improve sustainable practices (Lonergan, 2020). With Tech Central in full operation in the future, the entrepreneur ecosystem is envisioned to have expanded to have detailed directories and a re-designed visual ecosystem map. With additional specialised fields, the ecosystem will expand and form an even more complex map.

2.2 Analysis of opportunities and fragmentation in the current ecosystem

Strengths	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Sydney provides an ideal environment to promote innovation and pioneer new ideas • Sydney not only has a high population density that is great for business models that require scale, it also has attracted some of the best talent and large funding pools to support start-ups • Rapidly changing ecosystem • Introduction of new stakeholders • Grant And incentives that already exist <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Entrepreneur infrastructure programme ○ R&D Tax Incentive program ○ Innovative NSW
Opportunities	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • New technological advancements • More sustainable startups • Better education and communication channels for stakeholders to interact with
Fragmentation	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Limited awareness and knowledge surrounding startups • Lack of information regarding grants and incentives

2.3 The Levers in The Ecosystem

Through improving education and communication in startup creation and the development of entrepreneurial systems, we hope to foster startup growth that can be enhanced through funding and increased support from government and industry bodies. Stakeholders within the ecosystem can facilitate the development of this support for startups and small/medium businesses. The business department of the Australian government provides a range of resources through grants and programs for a plethora of business types ranging from beginner startups to established small/medium businesses. Business owners are able to apply for funding for apprentice employment and training, matched funding for startups and businesses from CSIRO Kick-Start, and support for training in self-employed businesses.

Education in startup/business development can also be improved with the involvement of incubators and accelerators such as Sydney startup hubs Bluechilli, Tank Stream Labs, and university programs. In integrating education, stakeholders such as UTS Startups, USYD INCUBATE, and the UNSW Founders Program are especially notable. Creating change within the entrepreneurial ecosystem of the Sydney CBD Areas will be central to establishing a support structure for the startup community, which targets current constraints of information overload and a lack of collaboration across stakeholders. These constraints will be targeted through the development of one central platform that enhances education and resources within the entire ecosystem. These leverages are intended to be design principles to guide future grants and incentives that are used as a primary method to support start-ups.

2.3.1 Lever 1: Integrating the entrepreneurial ecosystem through education and government Support with one central platform.

Current challenges startups face when applying for grants and incentives:

- Twenty per cent indicated a lack of information or people to complete applications
- Fourteen percent believed the business did not meet the eligibility criteria.
- Twenty-eight per cent specified a complex application process (The Committee of Sydney, 2015)

- “Australians do not necessarily feel that there are good opportunities to start a business or feel they personally have the skills to start a business, even though they likely know someone who has started a business and believe it is easy to start a business”. (Startup Status, 2020). The development of entrepreneurial skills from a younger age will provide individuals with the techniques and confidence to make a potential contribution to the innovation ecosystem within Sydney. Furthermore, the development of tech central.

Our Proposal

Eco+ 'an app to enhance your ECOcational purposes'

A more succinct process can play an important role within the entrepreneurial ecosystem to shape Sydney's future and furthermore, Tech Central to begin a startup. The City of Sydney should enhance both the collaborative and leadership role by working with the tech startup community and other levels of government to share the responsibility in designing Sydney as a leading innovative ecosystem. Providing better policy and collaboration opportunities can connect stakeholders with one another for a more competitive ecosystem and effective awareness among the community. (Beeche, 2014)

An online platform app called '**ECO+**' will be created to foster a more interconnected ecosystem with enhanced education and communication among stakeholders in the Community. Features of information regarding startups and connections to contact can be made available. We hope that the platform can make direct contact easier. The main target for this platform will be online education and the community both in social and learning areas to support current and future entrepreneurs.

ECO+ will target online education and collaboration aspects of digital communication that will utilise both social and learning sectors of valuable information and resources made available. Through the current challenges of limited education surrounding the startup community, we hope that direct communication can allow stakeholders to have direct access within the community.

The main feature for this app will include a discussion board for the stakeholder to ask for help and gain key insight into the current needs and problems faced in the startup community. The educational aspect will utilise the development of tech central by integrating it within educational institutions such as universities, schools, and technical and further education that can provide students with basic entrepreneurial skills and more practical and meaningful ways of learning. These skills vary from teamwork and leadership to strategic thinking and planning. (Indeed, 2021). It will also allow the ecosystem community to remain informed and aware of current activities within the environment.

Furthermore, entrepreneurial learning will assist in preparing children for “a future world of work that increasingly requires entrepreneurial learning and acting to navigate through one's career successfully, also outside of the business world.” (Earp, 2020). As a result, the next generation of students will have the ability to apply their skills to the entrepreneurial ecosystem within Sydney and furthermore, the development of Tech Central.

Therefore, through promoting education and communication with one online platform, we hope to reduce the current confusion faced by multiple communication channels and increase the awareness and education surrounding the entrepreneur skills and tools involved in the startup process.

Implementation for the App

Time allocation	Specific Plans
1-2 Years	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Collect data and market research on trends and insights from the community. E.g surveys and focus groups • Reach out to potential contributors and spread awareness through social media and UTS startup pages- will create a prototype for how it will look. • Testing and finalising: Trial the app as a prototype to a small group of users. Feedback and improvements gained will be considered in the app. • We believe following extensive research, ECO+ will be ready to launch. • The platform will be found on the App Store and in the form of a website to ensure accessibility for all users. • At launch, we will provide a unique QR code around the community and at universities to allow people to go directly to the app and get comfortable with the platform.
5 Years	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Engage with more stakeholders as the ecosystem evolves • Through word of mouth and social media, our community will be established and growing with annual events to advertise the app. • Following the launch of our app, we will take on feedback and continue to make improvements for the user over time. • We hope tech central, and the student will become fully integrated, creating a noticeable amount of jobs for students and future entrepreneurs developing a startup. • By 2027, we anticipate 10,000 users and a community that uses the app regularly.

2.3.2 Lever 2: Growth of Green Startups

Current Environmental Challenges within the city of Sydney

- Research suggests that there are a number of factors that impact the green economy which include “access to reliable and clear information, uncertainty in the policy environment and challenges in supply chain coordination” (The Committee of Sydney, 2015). Currently, there are many businesses that are poorly informed about the benefits and costs of becoming greener. The green star shows that ‘green buildings cost only 3% more to build than traditional buildings on average, which is less than most businesses expect’, emphasising the need for reliable information to make informed decisions about the green economy. Thus, the growth for sustainable startups. (The Committee of Sydney, 2015)
- The key challenges for Australian start-ups are access to capital and access to markets that are slow to shift away from traditional suppliers or products (Brennan, 2019)
- Between the years of 2018 and 2019, greenhouse gas emissions rose from 0.6%. (Hannam, 2019). This demonstrates how action needs to take place to create workspaces that are environmentally sustainable and implement plans into industries such as Architecture to reduce this number.
- We need to consider planning city-wide designs and spatial agreements of different land use. (Haris, 2019).

Our Proposal

Sustainacool - Continuous virtual workshops connecting industry experts and startups

Sustainacool consists of online workshops and events - connecting everyone from industry experts, universities & startups with a common passion for environmental sustainability. These workshops will run

initially every 3 months to assist startups with a passion for environmental sustainability with opportunities for growth within the current entrepreneurial ecosystem in Sydney. If successful, **Sustainacool** will expand and assist small to medium enterprises and eventually multinational corporations. The workshops will provide opportunities for collaboration and innovation as ideas for a greener future will be explored. **Sustainacool** also allows for individuals to gain feedback and learn new perspectives to further improve the current state of their businesses. Currently, the University of

Technology Sydney is assisting startups with the tools and techniques to help create environmentally sustainable solutions. These techniques can be further implemented through **Sustainacool** to assist businesses virtually as a result of the Coronavirus Pandemic. Furthermore, opportunities for further growth can be discussed to ensure multiple perspectives are considered before the implementation of future projects.

Implementation for our proposal - Sustainacool workshops and online events

Time allocation	Specific Plans
1-2 Years	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Contact relevant stakeholders in entrepreneurial ecosystem maps such as UTS Startups and Sydney Startup Hub and discuss the proposal. • Collect market research to understand the wants and needs of startups and entrepreneurs with project ideas and projects that could be catalysts for a greener future. • Collate data and find the trends • Gain access to funding e.g. "Building Partnerships Grants". • Select industry partners who are interested in being guest speakers • Plan with stakeholders and industry partners initial concepts for workshops and the duration of sessions • Finalise the content which will need to be covered for the first two sessions and ensure these discussions can be open to change. This is in case of developing news e.g. Coronavirus Pandemic • Promote Sustainacool on relevant marketing channels to gain as many participants interested in creating a greener future through startups and entrepreneurship
5 Years	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Engage with more stakeholders such as educational institutes and small to medium enterprises. • Continuously collate market research and how to improve Sustainacool workshops and events • Access more funding e.g. "Small to Medium Guarantee Scheme" • Complete the same process as in the 1-2 year plan but expand by inviting guest speakers from small to medium enterprises and multinational corporations as well as researchers. They can be from different industries but need to have a common ground for wanting to create an environmentally sustainable future.

3 Expected Value of Proposals

From the two proposals, they would bring valuable benefits to relevant stakeholders, specifically in areas of increasing the awareness of innovation to the community and building upon sustainability knowledge. Both proposals bring positive impacts in different fields.

Ultimately, the first proposal aids the younger generation by providing them insight and a foundation to enter an entrepreneur career. The educational institutes are vital stakeholders in imparting valuable knowledge and perspectives to their students for this proposal to work. The government and technological start-up community would be appealed activators as the awareness for innovation would increase and friendly rivalry between peers could fast-track the progression of the advancement of technology, more research and development discoveries and processes and innovation. Investors are given a wider diversity to invest in services, products or individuals that have the potential to succeed in the entrepreneur environment.

With a well equipped younger workforce with knowledge on start-ups and innovation, Tech Central draws closer to its goal of becoming Australia's Silicon Valley (NSW Government, 2020) and providing jobs for the society, leading to a growth of population in the heart of Sydney. Additionally, with a larger population, the reputation of Tech Central would increase which therefore gathers domestic and international talents to Sydney.

Furthermore, the second proposal increases the interactions between stakeholders through communicating better environmental knowledge and skills. Industry experts, universities, start-ups and scale-up enterprises are able to retrieve feedback, a variety of opinions and gain wider perspectives on sustainability and entrepreneurship. This proposal benefits all stakeholders as it gives an opportunity to strengthen the relationships between entrepreneurs, policymakers and architectural entities. This chance is given due to creating a social and informative digital platform that can be accessible to individuals nationally and globally.

Tech Central is said to be completed in 2035, highlighting the online platform to be useful in contemporary times as the proposal can be placed into action even during the COVID-19 pandemic. The stakeholders are given the prospect to put this proposal into operation and therefore expand the industry's entrepreneur ecosystem and understanding even before the usage of the Tech Central building.

Moreover, with the Australian government being majorly involved in the ecosystem, this proposal would support the plans of the City of Sydney (2017) is building a "public life and space to help create quality urban environments" and "to transform our city centre into a welcoming, public transport-oriented, green, connected, and distinctive place." Also, the residents of the area in Sydney are important stakeholders with hopes to improve their surrounding environment, having a stronger economy and having a more connective network with the citizens (City of Sydney, 2017).

References

- ArchitectureAU (2017). From convict architects to radical modernists: Footpath Guides' architectural <https://architectureau.com/articles/from-convict-architects-to-radical-modernists-footpath-guide-s-architectural-history-of-sydney/>
- Beeche, M., (2021, August 14). Can Sydney become the startup city that ecosystem stakeholders want it to be?. Startup Daily. <https://www.startupdaily.net/2015/08/can-sydney-become-startup-city-ecosystem-stakeholders-want/>
- Belitski, M., (2017, March). Expanding entrepreneurship education ecosystems. ResearchGate. https://www.researchgate.net/publication/312936923_Expanding_entrepreneurship_education_ecosystems
- Bennis, W., O'Toole, J. (2005, May). How Business Schools Lost Their Way. Harvard Business Review. <https://hbr.org/2005/05/how-business-schools-lost-their-way>
- Burgmann, M. & Burgmann, V., (2011) Green Bans movement. Dictionaryofsydney.org. https://dictionaryofsydney.org/entry/green_bans_movement
- City of Sydney. (2017, June 26). Sustainable Sydney 2030: Community strategic plan. City of Sydney. <https://www.cityofsydney.nsw.gov.au/strategies-action-plans/community-strategic-plan>
- Diaz-Garcia, M. C., Ben-Hafaiedh, C., Blackburn Ro. A. & Laveren, E. (2020, January). An introduction to Sustainable Entrepreneurship and Entrepreneur Ecosystems. Research Gate. https://www.researchgate.net/publication/345376062_An_introduction_to_Sustainable_Entrepreneurship_and_Entrepreneurial_Ecosystems
- Earp, J. (2020). Australia's largest teacher survey on enterprise education. Teacher Magazine. https://www.teachermagazine.com/au_en/articles/australias-largest-teacher-survey-on-enterprise-education
- GBCA. (2012) A Decade of Green Building - A history of the Green Building Council of Australia. Green Building Council of Australia. https://www.gbca.org.au/uploads/170/34474/A_decade_of_green_building_.pdf
- Government Architect NSW. (n.d.). About. Government Architect New South Wales. <https://www.governmentarchitect.nsw.gov.au/about>
- Hannman, P., (2019). Australia's greenhouse gas emissions set new seven-year highs. history of Sydney. <https://architectureau.com/articles/from-convict-architects-to-radical-modernists-footpath-guides-architectural-history-of-sydney/>
- HMC Architects. (2021). The Top 6 Sustainable Architecture Strategies for Public Building Design. <https://hmcarchitects.com/news/the-top-6-sustainable-architecture-strategies-for-public-building-design-2018-10-03/>
- Indeed Editorial Team. (2021). Expanding entrepreneurship education ecosystems. <https://www.indeed.com/career-advice/career-development/entrepreneurial-skills>.
- Loneragan, B. (2020, May 4). The Future of Architecture. Architecture Quote. <https://architecturequote.com/future-architecture/>
- M. Beeche (2015). Can Sydney become the startup city that ecosystem stakeholders want it to be?. Startup Daily. <https://www.startupdaily.net/2015/08/can-sydney-become-startup-city-ecosystem-stakeholders-want/>
- Stead, N., Oldfield, P. & Knapp, C. (2020, August 10). Designing hope: The role of architecture education in the climate crisis. ArchitectureAU. <https://architectureau.com/articles/designing-hope-the-role-of-architecture-education-in-the-climate-crisis/>
- The Committee of Sydney (2015, September). Building the start-up ecosystem in NSW: from grants to collaboration. <https://www.sydney.org.au/wp-content/uploads/2015/10/Building-on-the-start-up-ecosystem-in-NSW-from-grants-to-collaboration-Sydney-Issues-Paper-No.-9.pdf>
- Wade, M.(2016). Jobs and the economy. Sydney Morning Herald. <https://www.smh.com.au/interactive/2016/sydney2026/chapter7.html>

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